

LINGUA-DIDACTIC PROBLEMS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES
IN THE SYSTEM OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION.

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Abstract: Lingua-didactic problems of foreign language teaching in system of continuous education(schools, academic lyceums, vocational colleges) Hence the teacher should know exactly what his pupils are expected to achieve in learning his subject, what changes he can bring about in his pupils at the end of the course, at the end of the year, term, month, week and each particular lesson, i.e., he should know the aims and objects in foreign language teaching in schools. Hence the teacher should know exactly what his pupils are expected to achieve in learning his subject, what changes he can bring about in his pupils at the end of the course, at the end of the year, term, month, week and each particular lesson, i.e., he should know the aims and objects in foreign language teaching in schools.

Key words: professional communication in a foreign language, foreign language for special purposes, linguistic component.

The terms “aims” and “objectives” are clearly distinguished in accordance with the suggestion given by R.Roberts. Here is what he writes: “The term “aims” be reserved for long term goals such as provide the justification or reason for teaching second languages... the term “objectives” be used only for short-term goals (immediate lesson goal), such as may reasonably be achieved in a classroom lesson or sequence of lessons”.

Learning English language for special purposes enables future specialists in the field of art to acquire skills and abilities ensuring personal competitiveness and the chances of success in professional activities. It should be noted that competitiveness can be achieved only after overcoming communicative barriers, which, in particular, are foreign languages, therefore foreign-language professional competence is considered as the most important quality of a specialist. In this regard, professionally-orientated approach to teaching foreign languages for art students , which provides forming. students' ability to communicate using foreign languages in specific professional fields and situations, taking into account the peculiarities of professional creative thinking, plays a huge role. A distinctive feature of professionally oriented teaching English language is the maximum consideration the professional sphere specifics: its concepts and terminology, lexical-syntactic and grammatical features, the format of oral and written texts, situational features.

The goals and content of teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities are focused on the students major. The program of teaching foreign languages to students engaged in art formulates these goals as mastering by students the necessary and sufficient level of communicative competence to solve social and communicative problems in the fields of general cultural and professional activity, as well as mastering business communication skills, [1] which implies special approach to the learning foreign language process as a part of the specialization in art. In the process of mastering foreign language, students form and demonstrate the following both general and professional competencies: to be able to logically correctly, reasonably and clearly build oral and written speech; to master one of the foreign languages for international communication at a level that provides oral and written interpersonal and professional communications; to be able to generalize, analyze and critically evaluate works of art from their area of specialization. The essence of professionally orientated teaching foreign language lies in its integration with special majors. One of the fundamental methodological principles in teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university is the principle of professional communicative orientation, which implementing ensures the integration of the "Foreign Language" discipline into the general professional training of art students, using the experience gained in the course of studying special disciplines. Foreign languages teachers face the task to teach students, on the basis of interdisciplinary connections, to use foreign language as a means of systematically replenishing his professional knowledge.

Bachelor students of T. K. Zhurgenov Kazakh National Academy of Arts (cinema and TV, choreography, fine arts and DAA, theater and musical art departments, etc.) should participate in research work: make reports in English at different intra-university and outuniversity conferences about current trends in world art developing. Currently, within the framework of the trilingual education project at many major courses of the Academy, special disciplines in English language are introduced into the curriculum, for example, Film Criticism Skills, History of Art, History of European Theater, History of Kazakh literature etc. Thus, the functions of English language are expanding significantly, it not only helps to understand the content of foreign language texts, serves as an additional source of knowledge, but also helps to optimize oral intercultural communication in the professional sphere. The Bologna agreement opened the way for Kazakh graduates to the Western educational market and gave a real opportunity to continue their education abroad. In order to bring foreign language into line with the European recommendations on the levels of English proficiency, adjustments were made to the system of continuous training of university students. The

strategic direction for the development of education in modern society provides that graduates of higher schools in the field of art will: provides that graduates of higher education in the field of art will know one of the foreign languages of international communication at a level that provides oral and written interpersonal and professional communication, terminological vocabulary in the relevant direction, they will be able to conduct a discussion, to present their work outcomes in public, conduct professional correspondence in foreign language, will own general ideas about communication styles, basic methods of annotating, abstracting and translating literature on professional topics. Professionally-orientated teaching foreign language is now recognized as a priority in updating education. Foreign language communication becomes an essential component of the professional activities of specialists. The analysis of scientific and methodological sources showed that the term “professionallyorientated education” is used to refer to the process of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university, focused on reading literature on the majors, studying professional vocabulary and terminology, and more recently, on communication in the field of professional activities. [2, p. 306] As a rule, the term “professional communication” means teaching a foreign language, focused on the developing communicative competence in situations of professional communication.

In relation to the specialties of art, the linguistic component of teaching English is represented by a text library reflecting the classification of texts of this specialty; lexical material in the form of a terminological system for art and corresponding grammatical constructions. The methodological component provides for the ability to work independently with authentic texts and the formation of linguistic and contextual guesses. The texts are selected in accordance with the students' training majors: for example, for students of music majors “Note Values”, “Song Structure”, “Origin of Music”, “Major Scales”, “Minor Scales”, “Language of Music”, for students of theater specialties - “ The Origin of Theater ”, “ Classical Theater ”, “ Drama Theater ”, etc. In addition to the content, teachers should also pay attention to using forms and teaching methods that can ensure formation of students necessary professional skills. Thus, when teaching English at a non-linguistic university, achieving a level sufficient for its practical use in future professional activities is possible only with professionally orientated approach to its study.

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